

Use of electromyogram telemetry to assess the behavioural and energetic responses of rainbow trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Walbaum) to transportation stress

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Abstract

Behavioural and energetic responses of domesticated rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Walbaum) (mean fork length=440±45 mm) to a brief transportation episode were investigated. Fish implanted with radio transmitters measuring muscle activity (electromyogram; EMGi) were transported in a standard commercial shipping tank for 50 min by truck, and then allowed to recuperate for 48 h in stationary culture tanks. The EMGi telemetry data indicated that vigorous swimming activity occurred during transportation. Telemetry recordings also indicated that the fish's swimming activity returned to baseline levels within the 48 h period after transport. However, even beyond the 48 h resting period, the swimming performance (measured as critical speed and endurance) of transported fish was still impaired relative to non-transported controls ($P<0.05$). Respirometry measurements of fish taken after transportation indicated that oxygen consumption (V_{O_2}) was significantly elevated. The rise in V_{O_2} of post-transport fish could be attributed to handling procedures, as well as the intense swimming behaviour observed during transportation. Therefore, the behavioural responses of fish during transportation produced physiological consequences that persisted long after the transportation event. This study demonstrates the potential for utilizing behavioural measures, in concert with biotelemetry technologies, as tools to assess the impacts of routine aquacultural procedures on the health and welfare of captive fish.